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Reimagining the Indian Knowledge System through National Education Policy 2020

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Abstract : The development of the Indian education system is a unique journey, which extends from the ancient Gurukul system to modern policies. The National Education Policy 2020 is an important milestone in this journey, which aims not only to reform the education system but also to revive the Indian knowledge system. Adopting the **5+3+3+4** format, this policy emphasizes the timely development of students, which includes **physical, mental, social, cultural and moral values**. The Indian knowledge system which includes Vedas, Upanishads, and other scriptures, presents a rich heritage in the field of education. Under this policy, the budget for the study and association of Indian knowledge has been increased. This is not only an effort to raise the level of education, but is also a powerful medium to promote social, cultural and moral awareness among the youth. Through this policy, the youth of India will not only benefit from the repository of knowledge, but they will also be able to make their mark on the global stage with a new thinking and approach. If this policy is implemented successfully, it will prove to be a significant step in taking India in a new direction. Thus, this new approach of the Indian education system is leading towards a bright and prosperous future.

Keywords : Indian Knowledge System, Qualitative Improvement, National Education Policy 2020

Introduction:

The history and evolution of the Indian education system is a rich and varied journey, spanning from ancient times to the modern era. The system has not only been a medium for the accumulation of knowledge but has also played a vital role in the development of culture, ethics and social values. The ancient Indian Gurukul education system, known as the '**Guru- Shishya Parampara**', presented a unique model in the field of education. In this system, students lived with their Guru and delved deeper into the knowledge, leading to not only academic but also personal development. The Gurukul education system emerged in the Indian subcontinent about **5000 years ago**. It was a residential school system in which students lived with their Guru and studied various subjects. This system not only imparted academic knowledge, but it also helped in the development of social and moral values. The position of the Guru was extremely important in the society, and the disciples considered their Guru not only as a teacher but also as a guide and a role model of life. Currently, the Indian education system has seen many changes. Under the National Education Policy 2020, the need for many reforms in the field of education has been felt. Its main objective is to ensure the holistic development of students, which includes the

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development of physical, mental, social, cultural and moral values. This policy adopts the 5+3+3+4 format of education, which is designed to provide a timely and balanced education to the students. Under this new policy, there is a need to improve education at various levels. It not only talks about improving the curriculum, but also makes efforts to make teaching and learning methods more effective.

Indian Knowledge Systems (IKS) encompass a vast array of ancient system, including but not limited to Ayurveda, Vastu Shastra, Indian philosophy, classical music, and mathematics. **Raikwar (2023)** highlights the substantial contributions of ancient Indian knowledge to various domains, especially in the medical sciences.

Vedas, Upanishads, and other ancient texts hold an important place in the Indian knowledge system. These texts are not only a storehouse of knowledge but also provide guidance to understand various aspects of life. Education is considered not just an accumulation of knowledge but a means of understanding and applying it in various aspects of life. From this perspective, the aim of education is not just to score good marks in exams but to create a capable and responsible citizen. In today's era, when technological advancement and globalization have brought new challenges in the field of education, the Indian education system has to be prepared to face these challenges. Amidst online education, use of digital resources and competition at the global level, the Indian education system has to adapt to modernity while maintaining its values and system. Thus, the development of the Indian education system is a continuous process, which keeps changing with time. In a broader context, **Mandavkar (2023)** argues that IKS is not just a collection of historical knowledge but a dynamic system of thought that has evolved and can continue to evolve in the modern world.

It is not only a medium of knowledge, but it also plays a vital role in the development of culture, morality and social values. Today, when we talk about the future of education, we have to ensure that we maintain a balance between our ancient knowledge and modernity, so that our young generation can become a capable and responsible citizen.

Objective:

- To study the concepts of Indian knowledge System in National Education Policy.
- To study the challenges and their solutions coming in the way of qualitative improvement of Indian knowledge system in National Education Policy 2020.

Research Methodology :

The presented paper is conceptual and exploratory in nature and aims to enhance the understanding of Indian knowledge system in modern education policy and to add to the existing knowledge.

This research follows a qualitative methodology, as the nature of the topic necessitates an in-depth understanding of complex ideas, policies, and educational frameworks.

- **Literature Review:** Analysis of existing literature on the National Education Policy 2020, Indian Knowledge System, and related educational reforms.
- **Document Analysis:** Scrutinizing the text of the NEP 2020 to highlight provisions and recommendations related to the integration of IKS into educational practices.
- **Case Studies:** Investigating examples from educational institutions that have experimented with or incorporated elements of IKS, especially in relation to interdisciplinary education.

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The methodology will also incorporate comparative analysis, looking at how other countries have integrated indigenous knowledge systems into their educational frameworks.

It specifically studies secondary data sources, which are based on a wide range of academic books, peer-reviewed journals, conference papers and reliable internet databases. These secondary sources include research papers and dissertations, research books and other websites.

Indian knowledge system: The Indian culture, which has been rich and diverse in its journey from ancient times to the present day, is a unique cultural heritage. This system not only deeply embedded in various fields of culture, but also It also symbolizes the soul and identity of Indian society. The basis of Indian knowledge lies in texts like Vedas, upanyas, Mahabharata. The Indian knowledge system encompasses a variety of disciplines such as **science, mathematics, medicine, arts, and literature. Ancient Indian mathematicians invented zero and the decimal system**, which form the basis of today's mathematical thinking. **Ayurveda**, an important part of the Indian **medical system**, used natural remedies for health and well-being. In addition, Indian art and music have gained recognition around the world, reflecting the depth and diversity of Indian culture. In today's global era, the relevance of Indian knowledge system has increased even more. When we talk about the modern education system, it is necessary that we revive the Indian knowledge System and include it in contemporary education. **The National Education Policy 2020 also emphasizes that Indian knowledge system should be included at various levels of education, so that the new generation can be connected to its cultural heritage.** Many initiatives are being taken in this direction, such as developing courses related to Indian knowledge system in universities and providing training to teachers in this subject. This will not only make students feel proud of Indian culture, but will also help them become competitive at the global level.

The study of Indian knowledge not only reveals the treasure of knowledge but also teaches us that the purpose of knowledge is not just the accumulation of information but to serve humanity. Thus, Indian knowledge is a guide that not only connects us to our past but also inspires us towards the future. Therefore, it is necessary that we not only preserve the Indian knowledge system but also make active efforts to carry it forward so that future generations can also benefit from this invaluable heritage and assimilate it in their lives.

National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020): The National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020) is an important milestone in India's education system, which not only seeks to restructure the educational structure but also works to revive the Indian knowledge system. The aim of this policy is to make education holistic, inclusive and qualitative, so that all students can be provided a strong platform for their full development.

Many important initiatives have been taken in the direction of reform at various levels of education in NEP 2020. It takes into account all levels from primary education to higher education. It has been clarified in the policy that the objective of education is not only the accumulation of knowledge, but also to develop the ability to think, understand and problem solve in students. For this, Indian culture, history and system have been included in the curriculum, so that **students remain connected to their roots and can compete at the global level.** Under this policy, emphasis has been laid on making the education system

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multi-dimensional. In this, an attempt has been made to eliminate the boundaries between technical education, vocational education and general education. Students have been given the freedom to choose different options according to their interests and abilities. This will not only promote the interests of the students, but they will also be able to move in the right direction for their career. **NEP 2020 also has a special focus on teacher training and development.** It has been ensured that all teachers are made aware of the latest teaching methods and techniques, so that they can educate students in a better way. For this, both online and offline training programs will be organized. Apart from this, digital education has also been given priority in the policy. Given the need for online education during the **COVID-19 pandemic**, NEP 2020 talks about increasing the use of digital platforms. This will not only increase the reach of education, but students will also get easy access to various educational resources. Another important aspect of the National Education Policy 2020 is that it views education as a lifelong process. This means that education is not limited to school and college only, but it is important at every stage of a person's life. Under this, emphasis has also been laid on adult education and skill development, so that people can move forward in their career and contribute to the society. In conclusion, the aim of NEP 2020 is to establish a timely and inclusive education system that not only provides knowledge to students but also helps them become responsible citizens. This policy is aimed at making the Indian It presents a wonderful amalgamation of culture, tradition and modernity, which will help in empowering the future generations. Thus, NEP 2020 not only provides a new direction in the field of education, but it will also play an important role in the development of India.

Qualitative improvement in Indian education system: It not only raises the level of education, but also helps in the overall development of students. In the present times, when global competition and technological development are increasing rapidly, it has become necessary that we make qualitative improvements in our education system. **Qualitative improvement means increasing the quality at all levels of education, so that students not only get knowledge, but they are also endowed with moral, social and cultural values.** For qualitative improvement, first of all we have to understand the role of teachers. Teachers are not only communicators of knowledge, but they are also guides and motivators of students. Therefore, it is necessary to focus on the training and development of teachers. Teachers should be made aware of the latest teaching methods, techniques and content, so that they can teach students in a better way. For this, special attention has been given to the training of teachers in the National Education Policy 2020, which includes the Indian knowledge system. Apart from this; curriculum improvement is also an important part of qualitative improvement. According to **Savita Mishra (2020)**, the NEP's impact on teacher education will be profound, as it encourages teachers to not only adopt modern pedagogical practices but also embrace culturally relevant content.

The curriculum should be designed according to the interests and needs of the students. It should include practical knowledge, skill development and moral education. When students are interested in their curriculum, they learn more effectively. Debnath (2023) discusses the sustainable approach proposed by the NEP, which includes the incorporation of IKS into higher education, ensuring that the policy's objectives are met in a balanced and sustainable manner.

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Another important aspect for qualitative improvement is the integration of technology. In today's digital age, the use of technology is playing a vital role in education. By using e-learning, online courses and digital content, we can provide more engaging and interactive education to students. This will not only improve their learning process but will also prepare them to compete at the global level. Also, for qualitative improvement, it is important to take care of the mental and emotional health of the students. Education is not just the transmission of knowledge, but it is also an important part of the personality development of the students. Therefore, we should develop such an education system which keeps the students free from mental stress and gives them self-confidence. In conclusion, the aim of qualitative improvement is not just to raise the level of education but it is a holistic approach that helps in making students competent, ethical and responsible citizens. When we move towards qualitative improvement in education, we not only shape the future of our country but also lay the foundation of a better society. Thus, qualitative improvement is an essential requirement for the Indian education system, which will enable us to compete at the global level.

National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 has taken important measures for the Qualitative improvement of Indian knowledge system: This policy is not only a significant step towards reforming the education sector but also seeks to revive the rich repository of Indian culture, history and knowledge. Under NEP 2020, a one time approach to integrate Indian knowledge system into education system. It has been adopted. Its main objective is to make students aware of Indian culture and knowledge, So that they remain connected to their roots. For this, the curriculum includes the study of Vedas, Upanishads, and other ancient texts, so that students can experience the depth and diversity of Indian life. Additionally, the 5+3+3+4 format has been adopted in NEP 2020, which takes into account the physical, mental, and social development of children. Through this format, education has been made more inclusive and It has been made practical so that the students not only gain academic knowledge but also moral and social Also understand the values. This system gives students the necessary knowledge for their personal and collective development Provides skills. Special attention has also been given to the training of teachers. **This will ensure that teachers not only understand the depth of the subject but are also able to inspire students towards Indian culture and knowledge.** Online courses and workshops will be organized to equip teachers with modern teaching methods so that they can use the latest technologies. Apart from this, the budget for the study of Indian knowledge system has been increased in NEP 2020. This will ensure that adequate resources are available for the study and research of Indian knowledge system in educational institutions. Under this, special grants will be provided to develop and implement courses related to Indian knowledge system in universities. Another important aspect of NEP 2020 is that it considers the Indian knowledge system as a central pillar to make students globally competitive. This policy not only connects students to Indian culture but also inspires them to make their mark on the international platform. Finally, the measures for qualitative enhancement of Indian knowledge system under NEP 2020 will not only strengthen the education system but it will also generate pride and awareness among the new generation towards Indian culture and knowledge. **Sengupta (2018)** highlights the ethical access and benefit-sharing mechanisms necessary to protect traditional knowledge while ensuring that it can be accessed and utilized responsibly. In

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Traditional Knowledge in Modern India, Sengupta advocates for the creation of policies that safeguard indigenous knowledge, which is often vulnerable to exploitation or loss in a rapidly globalizing world.

Thus, NEP 2020 provides a platform to revive the Indian knowledge system. And it will prove helpful in getting it recognized at the global level.

Challenges and Solutions: Revival of Indian Knowledge system:

The Indian knowledge system, which has been an integral part of our culture and education for centuries, is facing many challenges today. In this era of modernity, when technological advancement and globalization have given a new turn to the field of education, the need to revive the Indian knowledge system has increased even more.

Ansari and Menon (2023) explore the challenges faced by knowledge management systems (KMS) in Indian schools, arguing that traditional educational structures are often too rigid to accommodate interdisciplinary knowledge systems like IKS. In this context, we have to understand the challenges that this system faces and take concrete steps to address them.

Challenges

1. **Pressure of modern education system:** The current education system, which is largely based on the western approach, is marginalizing the Indian knowledge system. Students are being prepared only to score good marks in the examinations, leading to a lack of in- depth knowledge and understanding. **Tiwari (2022)** discusses how the NEP empowers teacher education by encouraging educators to explore diverse knowledge systems and integrate them into their teaching practices.
2. **Information explosion:** The advent of the internet and digital media has made the dissemination of knowledge easier. But at the same time, it has become difficult to differentiate between correct and incorrect information. In this situation, it has become challenging to maintain the accuracy and authenticity of Indian knowledge system.
3. **Decay of Culture:** Indian culture and systems are being eroded due to the impact of globalization. The younger generation is getting attracted towards western culture, due to which their interest in Indian knowledge system is decreasing. **Gupta (2022)** also discusses strategies to implement the NEP's provisions on IKS, arguing that these reforms, if properly executed, will provide students with a broader worldview, combining scientific knowledge with indigenous wisdom.
4. **Lack of teachers:** Lack of expert teachers of Indian system is also a big challenge. If teachers are not given the right information and training about this system, then they will not be able to guide the students in the right direction.
5. **Lack of resources:** Lack of resources required for the study and research of Indian culture is also a major obstacle. There is a need for investment in this direction in government and private institutions. Aithal and Aithal (2020) explore how the NEP's structural reforms, such as the promotion of interdisciplinary education and the encouragement of research in indigenous knowledge systems, are crucial to fostering innovation within Indian academia

Solution

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Constitutional reform: Indian knowledge system should be included in the curriculum by reforming the education policy. Some steps have been taken in this direction in the National Education Policy 2020, but it needs to be made more effective.

1. **Use of digital platforms:** Indian Jan Parampara can be propagated using e-Diksha and other digital mediums. Connecting students with this system through online courses and webinars can be an effective way.
2. **Cultural awareness:** Special programs should be organized in schools and colleges to explain the importance of Indian culture and systems that will increase the interest of the young generation towards these systems.
3. **Training of teachers:** Special programmes should be organized to train teachers about the Indian knowledge system. This will enable them to give correct information to students about the importance and usefulness of this system.
4. **Research and Development:** More resources should be allocated to government and private institutions for the study and research of the Indian knowledge system. This will enable new discoveries and developments in this field.

The revival of the Indian knowledge system is not just an educational necessity, but it is also a question of our cultural identity and existence. We have to take concrete steps to face these challenges so that we can not only preserve our rich system but also take it forward. This is a collective effort, in which the government, educational institutions, teachers and society all have to work together. If we make efforts in the right direction, it is possible to revive the Indian knowledge system, which will be beneficial not only for our country but for the entire humanity.

Conclusion:

Revisiting the Indian knowledge system and its inclusion in the current education system has become an important need. This is not only a way to revive our ancient cultural values and teaching methods, but also a way to revive the Indian knowledge system. Not only is it a means to educate the students but it also instills pride in the new generation for being Indian. Under the National Education Policy 2020, the inclusion of Indian knowledge system in the curriculum will provide students with a rich and diverse education, which will make them competitive at the global level. Through this policy, students will not only get academic knowledge but will also have knowledge of moral, social and cultural values. This education system will help students understand their self-esteem and identity, which will keep them connected to their past and be aware of their future. The Indian knowledge system not only includes the Vedas, Upanishads, and other ancient scriptures, but also contains important elements such as the **Guru-Shishya parampara, collectivism, and tolerance**. The inclusion of these elements will provide a holistic approach to education to the students, making them not only efficient professionals but also responsible citizens. Steps taken in this direction will prove to be helpful in giving India a new identity on the global stage. If we properly implement the Indian knowledge system in our education system, it will not only raise the level of education but will also preserve our cultural heritage. In this way, future generations will be able to connect with their past and move towards a strong future.

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